

WOMEN IN SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: SCIENCE AND QUALITY EDUCATION

3RD INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

OLIMA AYOLNING SIFATLI TA'LIM UCHUN OLIB BORAYOTGAN IZLANISHLARI

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Kalit so'zlar: Xotin-qizlarni ijtimoiy-himoya qilish, inson kamoloti, o'qituvchi, yosh olim, pedagogik yutuqlar, muvaffaqiyatlar.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada mamlakatimizda xotin-qizlarga e'tibor berilayotgani, yaratilayotgan imkoniyatlardan samarali foydalanayotgan yosh olim va uning ijodi haqida ma'lumotlar keltirilgan. Ana shunday imkoniyatlardan oqilona foydalanayotgan yosh, iqtidorli, izlanuvchan pedagog sifatida o'z bilimi va pedagogik mahorati, zamonaviy pedagogik va axborot texnologiyalarni mohirona qo'llashi bilan jamiyatda pedagoglar e'tirofiga sazovor bo'lib, bilimi bilan jamiyat taraqqiyotiga o'z hissasini qo'shayotgan xotin-qizlar safida pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), Sarimova Dildora Soataliyevnaning alohida e'tirof etishni joiz deb topdik.

A woman scientist's research for quality education

Key words: Social protection of women, human development, teacher, young scientist, pedagogical achievements, successes.

Abstract: This article provides information about the attention paid to women in our country, the young scientist who is effectively using the opportunities created, and her work. The allocation of separate state quotas in higher educational institutions and the creation of conditions for our women to conduct scientific research are a proof of our word. In our country, the attention of the state policy is aimed at increasing the efficiency of the social protection system for women, raising their position in society and state management to higher heights. As a young, talented, aspiring pedagogue who wisely uses such opportunities, he is recognized by pedagogues in society with his knowledge

and pedagogical skills, skillful use of modern pedagogical and information technologies, and contributes to the development of society with his knowledge. We found it permissible to give special recognition to Sarimova Dildora Soataliyevna, Ph.D.

Исследование женщины-ученого для качественного образования

Ключевые слова:

Социальная защита женщин, развитие человека, педагог, молодой ученый, педагогические достижения, успехи.

Аннотация:

В данной статье представлена информация о том внимании, которое уделяется женщине в нашей стране, молодой ученой, эффективно использующей созданные возможности, и ее работе. Как молодой, талантливый, амбициозный педагог, грамотно использующий такие возможности, он признан педагогами в обществе своими знаниями и педагогическим мастерством, умелым использованием современных педагогических и информационных технологий, своими знаниями вносит свой вклад в развитие общества. Женщин-участниц, сочли допустимым особо отметить Саримову Дилдору Соаталиевну, доктора философии педагогических наук (PhD).

There are many professions in the world, each of them has its place and importance in life. But among them there is one great profession, on the basis of which all other professions are formed and develop. This is a teaching profession. The services of teachers are great in human education and development. We always feel that teachers have an inestimable contribution to any success and results that each of us has achieved in life.

The leader of our country said, "We are the representatives of the enlightened nation, who considered the teacher as great as a father and always honored him. When I think of a teacher, I imagine intelligent and modern, sincere and kind people who are the most dear and respected to me. Because this teacher gave lessons and education to all of us and raised us among our loving parents," he explains(1; 4 p).

Today, our women show selflessness not only in raising children, but also in various aspects of society. It's no secret that the place and status of women in

social life has acquired a special essence today. Because in her image lives the symbol of mother and coach. After all, in recent years, large-scale work has been carried out for the education of women in our country. The allocation of separate state quotas in higher educational institutions and the creation of conditions for our women to conduct scientific research are a proof of our word. In our country, the attention of the state policy is aimed at increasing the efficiency of the social protection system for women, raising their position in society and state management to higher heights. As a young, talented, aspiring pedagogue who wisely uses such opportunities, he is recognized by pedagogues in society with his knowledge and pedagogical skills, skillful use of modern pedagogical and information technologies, and contributes to the development of society with his knowledge. We found it permissible to give special recognition to Sarimova Dildora Soataliyevna, Ph.D.

D.S. Sarimova was born on July 22, 1988 in Chust district of Namangan region in an intellectual family. Graduated from Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizomi, majoring in Chemistry and Ecology. He started his career in 2009 as a chemistry teacher at the 82nd general education school of the Shaikhontokhur district of Tashkent city. In 2009, Dildora Sarimova, who started her creative career, took the first place in the city stage of the "Young Teacher" competition, which made her love her chosen profession even more. In 2010, he graduated from this university with honors. In 2012, he graduated from Nizamiy Tashkent State Pedagogical University. From 2013 until now, he has been working in various positions at the National Center for Training Teachers in Tashkent Region in New Methods. The scientist, who dedicated his life to science, is constantly working on himself in order to improve his pedagogical skills and experience. In addition, he created a video lesson on "Sulfur and its compounds" in cooperation with the Republican Multimedia Center, an electronic methodical guide called "Using the FLASH MX program to improve the creativity of chemistry teachers" and issued a certificate No. DGU No. 000763, "Production of

necessary substances in laboratory make and take apart. He created an electronic methodological manual entitled "Organization of a chemical experiment" and received IP CONSULTING CENTER Certificate No. 003259.

As a result of his regular participation in international and republican conferences with his scientific articles and theses during his pedagogical activity, he aimed to study the global experience and contribute to the development of the system of professional development. In 2016, she presented his experiences to chemistry teachers in the Republic at the Republican Forum in the field of "Education of Natural and Exact Sciences" as a moderator. received recognition. In 2016, in cooperation with the Center for the Development of Multimedia General Education Programs, created a video lesson on "Sulfur and its compounds" for the 8th grade and posted it for users on educational sites such as eduportal.uz, multimedia.uz, and the 10th grade held in August 2017 acting as a trainer at the training seminar on the implementation of the classroom textbook, on the implementation of the order of the Ministry of Education and Culture No. 34 "On continuous improvement of the professional skills of chemistry teachers of secondary schools" He took an active part in the video seminars held at the Republican Education Center with his lectures and popularized his work experience on the scale of the Republic and was awarded with the certificate of honor of this center. In 2018, he took an active part in the "Young Scientists" competition held by the trade union of the Republic of Uzbekistan and was awarded with a III degree diploma. In the same year, at Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizomiy, 13.00.02 - Theory and Methodology of Education and Training (Chemistry)" specialty "Improving the Competencies of Using Information and Communication Technologies of Chemistry Teachers in the Training System" as an independent researcher. accepted. During his scientific research, more than 50 articles and theses were published in scientific journals, republican, international and foreign conferences and magazines: "Using information technologies in teaching chemistry", educational- methodological and

methodological manuals have been published. In addition, he created a video lesson on "Sulfur and its compounds" in cooperation with the Republican Multimedia Center, an electronic methodical guide called "Using the FLASH MX program to improve the creativity of chemistry teachers" and issued a certificate No. DGU No. 000763, "Production of necessary substances in laboratory make and take apart. He created an electronic methodological manual entitled "Organization of a chemical experiment" and received IP CONSULTING CENTER Certificate No. 003259.

According to the idea that the value of progress lies in renewal and improvement, Dildora Sarimova is constantly improving her skills in the areas of industry. In the course of their activity, according to the reference number 02-02/4-406 of the Ministry of Public Education dated August 13, the methodical manual entitled "Methodology of using information technologies in teaching chemistry", "Increasing the creativity of chemistry teachers" Using the Flash MX program", "Formation and isolation of necessary substances in laboratory conditions", "Organization of a chemical experiment" electronic educational resource has been put into practice. Based on the requirements (modernity, informativeness, competence) set for the use of educational technologies and information and communication technologies in the process of professional development through these electronic methodical manuals, pedagogical and psychological aspects of the development of competence in the use of information and communication technologies in pedagogues, retraining and improving the qualifications of public education workers applied to the educational process in regional centers. The model of formation of information and communication competence of pedagogues in the process of professional development is based on the creation of active attitude of teachers (activity, motivation, mutual cooperation, self-development in the subject) and optimization of educational components based on special (professionally oriented knowledge and (reflecting the objective and subject orientation of skills) competencies were developed and put into practice. As a result, chemistry teachers have been using the opportunity to increase their

professional competence and improve their educational efficiency in the training courses. Dildora Sarimova has been awarded several times by regional, city, district authorities, women's committee of Uzbekistan for her work not only in education, in other public works, pedagogy, and community work, but also for her In recognition of his knowledge, activity, organization, and dedication to his profession, he was awarded the 2019 "Excellence of Public Education" badge by the Ministry of Public Education.

In 2021, D.S.Sarimova will receive a Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) degree in pedagogic sciences. 13.00.02 – Theory and methodology of education and training (chemistry)" Dissertation work on the topic of "improvement" is awarded by DSs. 02/30.01.2020. K/T. Successfully defended at the One-time Scientific Council formed on the basis of scientific council number 104.01.(2;21.p)

Currently, Dildora Sarimova works as the head of the "Methodology of Exact and Natural Sciences" department at the National Center for Training Teachers in New Methods of Tashkent Region. During the period of leadership and pedagogical activity, not only the National Center, but also the development of general secondary schools, improvement of the educational process, improvement of the quality of teachers' lessons, educational-methodical and material-technical education has been making a great contribution to the enrichment of resources with his advice. She works in cooperation with higher educational institutions of the United States of America, Germany, England and other foreign countries, actively participates in international scientific and practical conferences with his lectures.

Since 2021, he has been a member of the editorial board of For Joining Editorial Board of Eurasian Journal Of Humanities and Social Sciences ISSN Belgium. It makes a significant contribution to improving the professional skills of chemistry teachers in the region. Due to the fact that he was able to establish a disciplined and effective dialogue with the people around him in the region, he has been actively participating in the organization of various holidays and spiritual-educational events in the center and in other public works

SUMMARY

Promotes the content and practical effects of large-scale reforms implemented in the field of education in our country.

In the course of his pedagogical activity, she has her place and position among the team of the center with his diligence, responsible approach to tasks, inquisitiveness, tireless work to increase his professional and scientific potential.

As a highly qualified pedagogue, selfless and passionate person, he gained respect among his colleagues and listeners. In addition to being pedagogues and leaders in society, they are also mothers and beloved wives in the family. She is a loving mother of two daughters and two sons. D.S. Sarimova has her place both in the family and in society and is a strong-willed woman who sets an example for today's youth and can use every moment of her life meaningfully. and we wish his students to be happy forever.

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